

Brussels, 13 April 2018

COST 038/18

DECISION

Subject: **Memorandum of Understanding for the implementation of the COST Action “Building on scientific literacy in evolution towards scientifically responsible Europeans” (EuroScitizen) CA17127**

The COST Member Countries and/or the COST Cooperating State will find attached the Memorandum of Understanding for the COST Action Building on scientific literacy in evolution towards scientifically responsible Europeans approved by the Committee of Senior Officials through written procedure on 13 April 2018.

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING

For the implementation of a COST Action designated as

COST Action CA17127
BUILDING ON SCIENTIFIC LITERACY IN EVOLUTION TOWARDS SCIENTIFICALLY RESPONSIBLE EUROPEANS (EuroScitizen)

The COST Member Countries and/or the COST Cooperating State, accepting the present Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) wish to undertake joint activities of mutual interest and declare their common intention to participate in the COST Action (the Action), referred to above and described in the Technical Annex of this MoU.

The Action will be carried out in accordance with the set of COST Implementation Rules approved by the Committee of Senior Officials (CSO), or any new document amending or replacing them:

- a. "Rules for Participation in and Implementation of COST Activities" (COST 132/14 REV2);
- b. "COST Action Proposal Submission, Evaluation, Selection and Approval" (COST 133/14 REV);
- c. "COST Action Management, Monitoring and Final Assessment" (COST 134/14 REV2);
- d. "COST International Cooperation and Specific Organisations Participation" (COST 135/14 REV).

The main aim and objective of the Action is to leverage the strengths of diverse stakeholders (evolutionary biologists, education researchers, educators, museum professionals, the media) to foster networking that will stimulate research and best practices to promote scientific literacy in evolution. This will be achieved through the specific objectives detailed in the Technical Annex.

The economic dimension of the activities carried out under the Action has been estimated, on the basis of information available during the planning of the Action, at EUR 92 million in 2017.

The MoU will enter into force once at least seven (7) COST Member Countries and/or COST Cooperating State have accepted it, and the corresponding Management Committee Members have been appointed, as described in the CSO Decision COST 134/14 REV2.

The COST Action will start from the date of the first Management Committee meeting and shall be implemented for a period of four (4) years, unless an extension is approved by the CSO following the procedure described in the CSO Decision COST 134/14 REV2.

OVERVIEW

Summary

As citizens, we are confronted with a deluge of information and misinformation from the internet and the mass media. Scientific literacy, i.e. the ability to critically evaluate, apply and understand scientific knowledge and how it is produced, is therefore vital for responsible citizenship. It is a prerequisite for generating a knowledge-based society and for allowing citizens to make informed decisions. One of the most important fields of science is evolution, the foundation of modern biology. Evolutionary biology has great societal relevance and its findings have far-reaching implications for how we respond to climate change, drug resistance, issues of food security and controversies in modern medicine. However, it is frequently misunderstood or even rejected outright. This makes scientific literacy in evolution an ideal model to research approaches to improve the state of European scientific literacy. This Action will, for the first time, leverage the strengths of diverse stakeholders (evolutionary biologists, education researchers, educators, museum professionals and the media) to generate and analyse approaches used to improve public scientific literacy. Bridging differences in culture and education systems including participants from a wide range of countries and backgrounds is a source of innovation in itself. The expected result is to identify targeted strategies to raise levels of scientific literacy in Europe, thereby maximising Europe’s innovation potential. The Action will contribute to a culture of responsible, research and innovation (RRI) and will result in a more scientifically literate European citizenship, instrumental to implementing Europe 2020’s smart, sustainable and inclusive goals.

<p>Areas of Expertise Relevant for the Action</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biological sciences: Systems evolution, biological adaptation, phylogenetics, systematics ● Educational sciences: Education: training, pedagogy, didactics ● Media and communications: Museums and exhibitions ● Media and communications: Media and communications, social aspects of information science and surveillance, socio-cultural communication 	<p>Keywords</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● science literacy ● evolution ● science education ● outreach ● responsible science
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Specific Objectives

To achieve the main objective described in this MoU, the following specific objectives shall be accomplished:

Research Coordination

- (i) Reviewing and generating new data regarding the public’s scientific literacy in evolution across Europe;
- (ii) Identifying best practices across stakeholder groups in promoting scientific literacy in evolution;
- (iii) Promoting synergies between stakeholder groups to maximise the public’s science literacy;
- (iv) Ensuring efficient dissemination of the Action’s outputs to the target audience(s);
- (v) Promoting a culture of RRI amongst researchers, by enabling them to collaborate with other stakeholders involved in the Action and ensuring the successful dissemination to society.

Capacity Building

- (i) Build a high quality scientific and societal network of experts from COST Member Countries and from International Partner Countries.
- (ii) Provide a line of communication between the various stakeholders to increase public scientific literacy in evolution as a model for general science literacy.
- (iii) Knowledge exchange between fields and countries through placement of Early-Career Investigators

(ECIs) via Short Term Scientific Missions (STSMs) to boost capacity by sharing experiences and expertise of countries that have different approaches to and results from evolution education.

- (iv) Develop, train and generate materials to empower different stakeholders to effectively use their knowledge and skills to contribute to evolution and science literacy.
- (v) Developing a digital platform to exchange information between participants and enable the dissemination of the tools and knowledge produced.
- (vi) Promote outreach actions, activities and events built by interdisciplinary teams to foster public scientific literacy and fight “fake news”.

TECHNICAL ANNEX

1. S&T EXCELLENCE

1.1. CHALLENGE

1.1.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE CHALLENGE (MAIN AIM)

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a cross-cutting issue of Horizons 2020. A key priority of RRI is to “make results beneficial to a wider community” and one important aspect of this is science education. Scientific literacy – the ability to understand, evaluate and apply scientific content in our daily realities and to understand how it is generated – is crucial for citizens to make informed decisions on important societal issues. Lifelong science education is therefore needed to better equip citizens with critical thinking skills that underlie the EU priorities of “smart, sustainable and inclusive growth” (European Commission, 2010). Yet, about half of Europeans do not think that scientific knowledge is important in their daily lives. Furthermore, Europeans feel “less well informed than their level of interest demands” according to the Eurobarometer (2010) and the vast majority of Europeans are “not very active in science and technology issues”. How can this gap be bridged?

The EuroScitizen Action will assess the state of and identify best practices to tackle the gaps in European scientific literacy in the highly transdisciplinary field of evolutionary biology. Evolution is the cornerstone of biology and is fundamental to science as a whole. Scientific literacy in evolution is crucial for citizens to make informed decisions on societal issues including climate change, food security, growing antibiotic resistance, the spread of novel infectious diseases and biodiversity loss. Finally it is important in light of the recent, worldwide spread of hate groups and anti-intellectual claims, because social cohesion will arise, in part, through the recognition that human diversity is also a result of evolutionary processes.

Tackling this broad, diverse gap in scientific literacy is possible only through a coordinated research network involving a range of stakeholders: researchers in both evolutionary biology and education, science educators, museum and science-centre professionals, science communicators, the media and policy makers. To date, such a coordinated effort is lacking in Europe. By focusing on evolution, which is paramount to societal needs, this Action will serve as a model to study and develop best practices applicable to other fields of knowledge, promoting European scientific literacy in general.

1.1.2. RELEVANCE AND TIMELINESS

The ability to critically evaluate evidence is of particular relevance in today’s “post-truth” era where the internet has led to an unprecedented rise in the spread of “fake news”. In Europe, we are facing a serious challenge: despite an apparently strong “trust” in science, the tendency for many people to believe pseudoscientific claims (e.g. astrology or homeopathy) exemplifies both the general lack of interest in and importance attached to science by the public. It also reveals a skills gap in their ability to properly evaluate scientific evidence or understand how scientific knowledge is produced. These deficits affect their decision-making ability as reflected, for example, by the phenomenon of “vaccination hesitancy” or the reluctance of some sectors of the public to accept climate change. This situation could seriously impede achieving the Europe 2020 goals of “smart, sustainable and inclusive growth” (European Commission, 2010). Achieving such an economy requires citizens to master basic scientific-literacy and critical-thinking skills. Scientifically literate citizens should understand how scientific knowledge is generated and the way science “works” and use this information to innovate, foster inclusion and economic growth, and solve societal problems.

Evolution provides an ideal platform to begin improving public science literacy in Europe and one with immediate benefits because it affects decisions linked to pressing societal challenges such as food security, climate change or medicine. A better understanding of human evolution is also essential for inclusive societies and for raising Europe's education targets. Evolution is also unique among the sciences insofar as it often lacks public acceptance and has strong political overtones (e.g., it has very recently been banned in Turkey) despite being a well-established scientific theory. As Blancke et al. (2014) show, acceptance of evolution varies widely across Europe, with Iceland being the least likely to reject it (7% of the public) and Cyprus being the most (36%). The European Parliament has long recognised the importance of teaching evolution in an understandable way as well as the dangers of creationism in education (Council of Europe, 2007). To date, only one EU-funded project has focused on the understanding and acceptance of evolution, the BioHEAD citizen project (Carvalho, 2004) which focused on human evolution, people's understanding of it and the way it was presented in school textbooks. However, this project is now almost a decade old and involved participants from only four countries. Since then, many social and political changes have occurred both globally and in Europe that might affect literacy in evolution. Thus, as valuable as the project was, there is still a widening gap to be filled.

The value of this Action lies in bringing together disparate stakeholders from across Europe with a shared interest in evolution literacy. Together, the network can leverage each group's strengths to develop more effective messages that are relevant to Europe's citizens. Evolution – with its direct societal impacts – can serve as an ideal model for scientific literacy more generally. This will contribute towards a culture of RRI and to attaining the goals outlined in Europe 2020.

1.2. OBJECTIVES

1.2.1. RESEARCH COORDINATION OBJECTIVES

The main aim of the Action is to leverage the strengths of diverse stakeholders (evolutionary biologists, education researchers, educators, museum professionals, the media) to foster networking that will stimulate research and best practices to promote scientific literacy in evolution. The following Research Coordination Objectives will be met: **(i)** Reviewing and generating new data regarding the public's scientific literacy in evolution across Europe; **(ii)** Identifying best practices across stakeholder groups in promoting scientific literacy in evolution; **(iii)** Promoting synergies between stakeholder groups to maximise the public's science literacy; **(iv)** Ensuring efficient dissemination of the Action's outputs to the target audience(s); **(v)** Promoting a culture of RRI amongst researchers, by enabling them to collaborate with other stakeholders involved in the Action and ensuring the successful dissemination to society.

Key deliverables of these activities will include: **state-of-the-art summaries of the outcomes of the Action tailored for each stakeholder and policy briefs** to help decision and policy makers make evidence-based decisions regarding the education of future citizens; **surveys** based on common research tools will provide comparable data between the participating countries to yield **a novel, continuously updated and stratified dataset** about the acceptance and understanding of evolution across Europe; **guidelines** for each stakeholder for the deployment of existing and newly created tools, resources and methods; **a community** composed of different stakeholders dedicated to maintaining and developing the highest standards in improving scientific literacy using evolution as a model. The diversity of this community will impact both the deliverables themselves (by ensuring they meet the various stakeholders needs) as well as their dissemination (by ensuring they reach a larger audience than readers of peer-reviewed publications, in particular in respective stakeholders' communities).

The existence of such community will benefit all its members. Education researchers will benefit from a broad European network by establishing continent-wide contacts and collaborations with other education researchers throughout Europe with their different challenges and perspectives. Evolutionary biologists will benefit from this Action through **improved access to education researchers, science communication and media professionals**, all of whom can provide concrete guidance as to how they can improve their science-communication skills. The media will gain opportunities to interview scientists.

1.2.2. CAPACITY-BUILDING OBJECTIVES

The Action has targeted the following Capacity-building Objectives:

- Build a high-quality scientific and societal network of experts from COST Member Countries as and from International Partner Countries;
- Provide a line of communication between the various stakeholders to increase public scientific literacy in evolution as a model for general science literacy;
- Knowledge exchange between fields and countries through placement of Early-Career Investigators (ECIs) via Short Term Scientific Missions (STSMs) to boost capacity by sharing experiences and expertise of countries that have different approaches to and results from evolution education;
- Develop, train and generate materials to empower different stakeholders to effectively use their knowledge and skills to contribute to evolution and science literacy;
- Developing a digital platform to exchange information between participants and enable the dissemination of the tools and knowledge produced.

A series of outcomes will arise from these activities, with the following key deliverables:

- Creating the conditions for participating in R&D projects (H2020 and specifically SWAFS);
- 10 STSMs over the four years to broaden the experience of ECIs and other members as well as to foster the European and worldwide network in evolution literacy;
- Academic Training Schools for ECIs and more established action members to provide opportunities for mentoring and knowledge sharing (see Section 3.1.1);
- Seminars and workshops to stimulate sharing of information on the progress (Section 3.1.1).

1.3. PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE-OF-THE-ART AND INNOVATION POTENTIAL

1.3.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE STATE-OF-THE-ART

Science literacy and active citizenship are widely recognised as important factors for a democratic society (Snow & Dibner, 2016). General and unobstructed access to scientific education and information is considered one of the most fundamental rights in modern, developed societies, with scientific literacy being crucial to achieving the European Union's goals. With information being more readily attainable than ever before through mass-media and the internet, citizens are bombarded daily with huge amounts of information related to their health, environmental threats and everyday consumer choices. Decisions regarding diverse policies and regulations (e.g. vaccination programs, recycling policies, or environmental conservation strategies) are often deeply rooted in modern science and the current state of knowledge about our world. Faced with these challenges, scientifically literate citizens will be better able to face the scientific and technological challenges that they encounter during their daily lives and to make informed decisions to benefit themselves, their families, and society. Improving scientific literacy is therefore considered both a fundamental requirement for and a major challenge to society (cf. Horizon 2020 Framework). Developing scientific literacy on the societal level requires active involvement of and collaboration between diverse actors (researchers, communication and education experts, formal and informal educators), and civil society (Hazelkorn et al., 2015). Evolutionary biology – a dynamic and fast developing field of science – represents an excellent topic to use as a model.

Evolutionary theory permeates all fields of biology and serves as a cornerstone to understand all biological discoveries. Evolution is **a major concept that needs to be understood by all citizens because it influences their lives and decisions**. Improvements in agriculture are largely due to evolution by natural selection, with natural selection also accounting for the rise in antibiotic and pesticide resistance as well as informing the design of new technologies and methods to manage such problems. Evolution affects our understanding of the consequences of human-induced environmental changes (e.g., global warming, alterations of water availability across biomes, intensification of agriculture and

expansion of urbanised landscapes, and the spread of antimicrobial-resistant organisms in natural environments). Understanding evolution is also central to the advancement of medicine: the newly established field of “evolutionary medicine” is devoted to using the principles of evolution to study, preclude and treat human illness (Fozail, 2017). Evolution is also an excellent topic to explore the Nature of Science by enabling us to address the differences between religious beliefs, common sense and science; to stress the importance of evidence for science and the variety of types of evidence that can be used to explore scientific ideas; and to perceive science as a human endeavour. Altogether, the large number of daily life applications of evolution provide ideal contexts for approaches that build on individuals’ previous knowledge to foster engagement in scientific practices, and scientific and ethical discussions that require negotiation (Rocard et al, 2007).

Nevertheless, there exists a clear disparity between the acknowledgement of evolution as a well-established theory in academic circles and its misunderstanding or outright rejection by the public. For example, in 2017, in Turkey and in Poland, evolution was removed from high school textbooks on the grounds that students lacked the necessary scientific background to understand the “debate” (Turkey) or because the curriculum was “overloaded” (Poland). Clearly, there is a communication problem between the scientific community, decision makers and the general public such that little progress appears to have been made to fight anti-evolutionary claims on national and international grounds.

Thus, despite its importance, pioneering improved science literacy in evolution remains challenging. The BioHEAD citizen project concluded that evolutionary misconceptions still pervade the teachers’ community. These results led them to conclude that **there should be an analysis of the students’ conceptions about evolution at several school levels**, especially given that evolution **is either absent or given little importance in the school syllabi**. Indeed, most educational programs in Europe treat evolutionary theory as a side-topic that, at best, is usually referred to after other biological content has been covered and therefore is often neglected or even omitted altogether. This is especially true at levels where proper communication of science has the greatest impact on future scientific literacy (e.g., early school learning or secondary schools). Changing this scenario will require changes in both formal and informal education practices, investment in professional development for teachers, and a strong collaboration between distinct stakeholders (Hazelkorn et al., 2015).

Some attempts to achieve this synergy are already underway. **Informal learning** initiatives attract considerable audiences and popularise evolutionary knowledge in an impressively effective way (e.g. the traveling “Darwin” exhibition which went to more than 22 locations attracting hundreds of thousands of visitors, “The Evolution collection” by the Botanic Garden of the University of Bristol, and Darwineum at the Zoo Rostock). **Media** also seem to pay more attention to evolution-related stories although the outcomes are often ambiguous because they can also create or reinforce misconceptions or shape the public’s attitudes about **scientists**. Science journalists often lack sufficient scientific training or are under pressure to sensationalise “the story” to improve its chances of publication. Finally, some scientists have embraced a direct engagement with the public, with an effective way being **citizen science**, a powerful tool to promote the public understanding of science.

Evolutionary biology, often perceived as a history-centric science, is actually a fast-paced scientific discipline with novel topical developments such as e.g. the application of epigenetics to understand the postnatal effects on a baby of the mother’s dietary habits during pregnancy. However, most modern achievements and applications of evolutionary theory to daily life, are ignored in educational efforts. This deeply compromises students’ ability to understand biological systems, which are still being shaped by evolutionary processes. It is therefore surprising that evolution, a topic of such scientific power so far has not attracted a coordinated, international action aimed at analysing its current state of understanding and improving its dissemination at all levels. The Action network with its societal relevance evolution can offer the ideal model to develop approaches that can be applied to science literacy in general. Only with a coordinated effort can we ensure that scientific literacy – and evolution in particular – gains proper momentum to change minds and to educate future generations.

1.3.2. PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE-OF-THE-ART

Today, about 15 years after the completion of the BioHead citizen project, the socio-cultural-religious national context of most European countries has changed and teaching, understanding and interest in evolutionary theory are rapidly eroding across Europe. In this new sociological landscape, there are no coordinated initiatives in evolution education and literacy, let alone ones that integrate the expertise and innovation from various stakeholders (see Fig. 1) with the goal of promoting the public's scientific literacy in evolution.

Figure 1. Each stakeholder has a key role to play to address the following objectives of the Action:

Assessment: Developing tools to assess the European public's acceptance and understanding of evolution · **Formal education:** Scientists specialising in formal education will work with the teaching community to analyse how evolution is explored in different national school curricula and analyse in- and pre-service teachers' scientific literacy and pedagogical knowledge. **Informal educators:** will investigate the impact of informal learning opportunities on the public's scientific literacy · **Media:** Analysing the role of the media and science-journalist interactions and suggesting best practices. The media are also expected to act as a key conduit for dissemination. **Scientists:** (i) Assessing the role of scientists in promoting

science literacy in evolution. (ii) Analysing the potential of citizen science as a tool for public engagement in evolution. · **All:** Cross-sector collaborations between stakeholders (arrows) will lead to effective ways of promoting scientific literacy.

This Action goes beyond the State-of-the-Art as it will support networking opportunities that will enable the following research:

Assessing the level of acceptance and understanding of evolution in relevant groups of society. Obtaining a clear picture of the opinions of Europe's citizens on evolution has been difficult. To date, research in this area has been conducted only on small scales or using different research instruments, which is problematic both for reasons of reliability (Smith & Siegel, 2016) and comparability. Moreover, the most commonly used inventory to measure attitudes towards evolution, the MATE scale, has been criticised for several reasons (McCain & Kampourakis, 2016). Miller (2006) represents the only relevant research on a large scale (about 1000 people from many countries), but was a meta-analysis of several, not necessarily comparable evaluation instruments all based on multiple choice questions. This Action will create a unified and standardised set of surveying and statistical methods to maximise the reach, comparability and impact of its results for future studies.

Assessing and improving students' and teachers' literacy in evolution. Several authors and scientific organisations argue that evolution should be explored across the entire students' educational spectrum starting with kindergarten and with increasing levels of complexity. The lessons should be linked with examples from daily life, local culture and societal problems. However, it is unclear how these goals can be translated across Europe, where each country (or regions within them) has its own distinct syllabus. The international networking opportunities offered by this Action will enable collecting and analysing the necessary information from each participating country to propose national/regional changes taking into account the entire course of study and local issues.

For effective student learning, teachers require up-to-date knowledge about the content and skills they are asked to teach (content knowledge, CK) and how these can be developed in their classrooms (pedagogical content knowledge, PCK) in the context of their students and the curriculum (Sadeghi and Zanjani, 2014). In those countries and instructional levels in which a teacher is responsible for cross-disciplinary teaching (e.g. primary school), updated CK and PCK is needed, especially given that misconceptions about evolution are common among teachers across Europe and across school grades. In the present Action, we will analyse the impact of both formal and non-formal educational programs and

professional development on teacher's CK and PCK on science and evolution at all educational levels. Through it, we will identify best practices that can empower teachers to contribute to evolution literacy.

The impact of informal learning environments on the public's scientific literacy in evolution. Despite the huge promise that natural history museums, botanical gardens and science centres have as environments to promote lifelong learning in evolution, the effectiveness of teaching evolution in such settings in Europe has received little attention. In the US, studies have shown that teaching evolution in a museum setting can be highly effective and that even a single visit to an evolution exhibition can improve visitors' understanding of evolution and resolve many misconceptions (Spiegel et al. 2012). This Action therefore aims to, for the first time, evaluate the effectiveness of European museums and science centres in promoting lifelong learning in evolution in informal settings.

The role of the media in scientific literacy in evolution. Evolution literacy suffers because scientists often fail to use best practices in science communication while journalists often lack the scientific background to best understand science as a process. Therefore, this Action aims to facilitate a dialogue between scientists and journalists (e.g. by supporting opportunities such as workshops) to identify best practices in science-media interactions in communicating evolutionary science.

Assessing the role of scientists in promoting scientific literacy in evolution. Scientists have a crucial role to play in engaging the public and, although most of them acknowledge the importance of developing strong ties to society, only very few are truly involved in scientific outreach. The Action will review the different ways that exist to foster their engagement and support Training Schools in science communication for scientists, to identify best practices promoting efficient interactions (e.g. public outreach events or citizen-science initiatives). This will promote socially responsible scientists dedicated to a culture of RRI.

Establishing a network of stakeholders. Cross-sector collaboration and regular opportunities to meet are required. Joint workshops bringing scientists, educators, media professionals and outreach organisations together will promote trust, exchange of knowledge and collaboration. Bridges between formal and informal education will also be promoted.

1.3.3. INNOVATION IN TACKLING THE CHALLENGE

The Action rises to the challenge of finding novel ways for diverse stakeholders to collaborate closely to improve scientific literacy in evolution in Europe. Such cross-sector and European-wide collaboration is a source of innovation; it will enable, for the first time, experiences to be shared and national and cultural differences with regard to this important topic to be discussed and resolved. Already, the Action network contains 23 countries, with a 56.5% ITC inclusiveness score. The Action will innovate as it will overcome previous obstacles from the use of different and ambiguous research tools by researchers from different countries. Further innovations include finding methods to promote lifelong learning in evolution from kindergarten to adulthood. Best practices to communicate the theory of evolution sensitive to requirements of different age groups, educational levels, cultures and religions will be implemented. By placing evolution in a societal context and making it relevant to people's daily lives, and by fostering links with the media to ensure effective dissemination the results of the Action will promote a higher level of scientific literacy in Europe. This will lead to more responsible citizenship thereby enabling Europe 2020's smart, sustainable and inclusive growth.

1.4. ADDED VALUE OF NETWORKING

1.4.1. IN RELATION TO THE CHALLENGE

Public scientific literacy is clearly a complex, multi-disciplinary issue that will resist simple solutions. The core focus of the Action is to bring together the various stakeholders involved in this area. Actors from these different fields rarely overlap and usually do not engage one another directly, although their work is often complementary and will benefit greatly from shared skills and areas of expertise. The Action will therefore provide a unique opportunity to bridge the gaps that exist between researchers and practitioners. The sharing of expertise will facilitate the development of deliverables that fit each stakeholder's needs and thus encourage their use in contrast to recommendations that are disconnected from actual practice. The network itself is thus key to the success of the Action.

By breaking cross-disciplinary and geographic boundaries, we will develop a collaborative approach to address scientific literacy in evolution. For example, already the inclusion of 13 Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs) will provide us with a better understanding of the realities in these often under-represented countries, where the problem of the acceptance of evolution and public science literacy is of particular relevance and importance.

1.4.2. IN RELATION TO EXISTING EFFORTS AT EUROPEAN AND/OR INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

To date, no transdisciplinary and cross-sector network in Europe focusing on the scientific literacy in evolution exists. More generally, there are also no COST networks addressing the equally important topic of scientifically literate European societies. However, there is clear interest in the subject. For example, the importance of these issues was raised at a recent meeting in February 2017 dedicated to the public understanding of evolution in Europe. The outcomes of this meeting were highlighted in an editorial in *Nature Ecology and Evolution*, which pointed out that **“although problems with the public perception of evolution does not receive as much attention in Europe as it does in the United States, this does not mean that they do not exist, and also that public understanding and acceptance of evolution vary considerably across the continent”**.

Thus, this Action builds on recommendations from the BioHEAD Citizen project that stressed the need for an extended analysis of people who reject evolution and teachers' perceptions on evolution. It also complements current work on SETAC (Science Education as a Tool for Active Citizenship), which targets the European priorities of health, energy and climate change, but with a focus on formal and informal education. The Action also implements many of the recent recommendations in the report “Science education for responsible citizenship” by the Expert Group on Science Education (2015). For example, many work packages are designed to “initiate actions which strengthen links across formal and informal education” (Working Groups 2 and 3). By specifically involving scientists (Working Group 5) and gender balance (57.4 % women), the Action promotes RRI, a cross-cutting issue of the Horizons 2020 program.

In addition to its European focus, the Action will forge links with global collaborators. The topic is of obvious interest in the USA where evolution acceptance rates are very low relative to European countries, with the exception of Turkey (Miller et al. 2006). Previous research e.g. Barnes & Brownell (2016) in the USA funded by the NSF (0910115 and DGE-1311230) addressed the religious beliefs of college instructors when teaching evolution. This and other similar research can be linked to this Action to more comprehensively uncover the diverse underlying factors affecting acceptance of evolution and provide an important comparison. These kinds of studies have led to more effective curriculum, professional development, and informal education materials such as the Understanding Evolution website, traveling exhibits and online resources, and the Concord Consortium's Evolution Readiness program. The IPC Participants will seek collaborations with institutions specialising in evolution education and outreach in the US. The research and resources developed in the US can be leveraged to promote the goals of this Action to more comprehensively uncover the diverse underlying factors affecting acceptance of evolution and provide an interesting comparison and perspective and the opportunity for cross-Atlantic collaboration.

2. IMPACT

2.1. EXPECTED IMPACT

2.1.1. SHORT-TERM AND LONG-TERM SCIENTIFIC, TECHNOLOGICAL, AND/OR SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACTS

Scientific and technological impact. According to the thematic objectives of the EU for the programming period 2014–2020, one priority of the framework will be “investing in education, training and vocational training for skills and lifelong learning”. The Action will meet this objective by proposing a comprehensive integration of scientists, educators and policy influencers across Europe to learn from one another and collaborate on a well-accepted and nevertheless controversial topic of evolution. The short-term scientific and technological impact will be realised primarily through: (i) the generation of valuable new data and guidelines for gauging the levels of scientific literacy in Europe, ii) the generation of recommendations and best practices across a range of disciplines and countries/cultures, (iii) the creation of bridges between sectors to tackle the issue of scientific literacy in evolution and (iv) the efficient dissemination of this information to the relevant audiences. The outcomes of the Action will also have broader scale, long-term implications on the Nature of Science and other scientific disciplines. We expect an improved reception of science and the scientific community as a whole by society as well as of science-based technological endeavours, including increased interest in technological initiatives that explicitly target evolutionary mechanisms as key tools. The Action will also likely contribute to implementing the RRI objective of the Horizon 2020 framework.

Socioeconomic and policy impact. As emphasized in the report “Science Education for Responsible Citizenship”, science education “should balance requirements of breadth and depth of knowledge about science to ensure young people and adult learners are both motivated for learning and equipped to fully engage in scientific discussions and decisions and to facilitate further and deeper study” and also “support arts-based initiatives with a STEAM focus, e.g. film, media, visual arts, etc. to develop resources promoting science learning, positive views of science and scientific culture”. The formal network of the Action aligns with these recommendations by promoting evolutionary biology in particular and the scientific literacy of society in general. In the long term, this Action will impact positively on the public perception of science and the way school curricula are built and evaluated in this context.

2.2. MEASURES TO MAXIMISE IMPACT

2.2.1. PLAN FOR INVOLVING THE MOST RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS

The most relevant **stakeholders of this Action are evolutionary biologists, education researchers, science educators, museum and science centre professionals, science communicators, the media, policymakers and the general public**, who are central to this effort. The Action will initially be catalysed through motivated stakeholders that are leaders in their respective fields and extended through their existing contacts. Additional stakeholders will be contacted via social media; congress, seminars, workshops and other activities attended by stakeholders; and field-specific platforms (e.g., evolutionary biologists via listservers such as evoldir; education researchers via national associations; teachers via existing educational platforms and networks such as e-twinning, Scientix or Science on Stage; informal educators and science communicators via EcSite newsletters; and the media through institutional communication offices). The media play an especially important role in this regard because they are both a target stakeholder and also act as a key lever for dissemination.

The **Management Committee (MC)** will create a stakeholder strategy that is balanced across COST Member Countries, stakeholder groups, genders and career stages. The strategy will be reviewed on an annual basis and updated as needed.

Action Members. The Action will update all members about the activities of the network, both asking for and addressing their input as well as promoting participation in Action discussions. Different channels

of communication will be used (e.g. direct communication during member meetings; activities at conferences, scientific and educational activities; social media promotion and discussions; an online platform to display and exchange information and news about the Action; or e-mail newsletters).

Stakeholders that are not Action Members. The Action will prioritise contacting scientists, educators and science communicators in ITCs because these potential members will enrich the Action with relevant information about the diversity of cultural, educational and practical aspects in underrepresented European countries. The members of this Action will work to reach stakeholders in these countries through national and international science and educational networks, bilateral collaborations, social networks and the Action website as well as by organising Action meetings associated with international scientific conferences and by specifically inviting them to Action activities. The Action will also encourage potential stakeholders to become Action members by stressing the opportunity to contribute to long-term scientific educational advances and having access to complementary expertise.

2.2.2. DISSEMINATION AND/OR EXPLOITATION PLAN

A key goal of this Action is the efficient dissemination of the information gained, tailored to the needs of each target audience. Each Working Group (WG) will be responsible for its own dissemination strategy with detailed audience development and output. The plans will be reviewed by the Management Committee at the initial meeting and should (i) encourage member participation, (ii) comply with the COST mission and (iii) assist opportunities for feedback throughout the Action. Minutes of the meeting will be available on the Action website to promote transparency throughout the Action.

Scientific community. Peer-reviewed publications prioritising open-access journals will disseminate the key results of the Action to the scientific and science-education communities. These will be complemented by onsite actions such as presentations or stands at conferences. Scientists will also be encouraged to disseminate their research to the public by communicating relevant examples of evolutionary research and concepts through outreach actions including “public-scientist speed-dating events”, citizen projects, summer science schools and open days, and science-society debates and by encouraging an active media presence. Such initiatives should also draw the attention of local policymakers.

Teachers. Dissemination of material will take place through social networks, the Action website and existing educational platforms and networks (e.g. e-twinning, Scientix or Science on Stage). The Action will offer them content, resources and guidelines that promote and facilitate the teaching of evolution.

Informal educators. The results of the Action will be presented at both local science communication conferences by Action members and at EcSite, the largest European science centre and museum conference. Workshops for practitioners at these events will further help to disseminate this information.

Funding agencies, and policy makers. Short communications, reports and media articles will be produced highlighting the major resolutions of the Action and recommended best practices. Politicians will also be invited to any events related to the Action.

Media. In this Action, the media function as both stakeholders and levers. Press releases oriented to local media will highlight the cooperation of local researchers, schools and institutions as a part of a European effort to increase social understanding and acceptance of evolution. Moreover, efforts will be made to improve the journalists’ understanding of the science by providing them with clear, accurate contents to publish, which will help motivate them to publish the science while simultaneously minimising potential misunderstandings and misconceptions. The respectful relationship that will be fostered as a result of this Action will ensure the correct dissemination of Action outcomes.

General public at large. The Action will include the public in its scientific, educational and social efforts through diverse, participative activities in both online and on-site formats (e.g., open discussions, conferences, seminars, workshops and informal activities including science outreach and citizen science). In addition, the public will also have access to the data, information and resources from the collaborative efforts via the Action website and be able to provide their feedback at critical stages of the Action (e.g. survey designs). The media is also expected to facilitate outreach efforts with the public.

The Action will use several communication channels to update all interested audiences on its progress: **a website** describing the Action, all involved participants and especially the Action's Management Committee; **a newsletter** linked to the Action's website detailing the progress of the Action, open meetings and workshops, published documents and reports; **participation in external events** (e.g. conferences, workshops, and outreach initiatives) to promote the outcomes of the networking achieved through the Action; **presenting specific results**, reports and policy initiatives to educational institutions to form part of developing strategies in future educational curricula; **social media channels** devoted to disseminating general results of the Action and other updates (in synergy with the Newsletter). For this purpose, a logo and associated graphic identity and visual support will be designed and produced professionally to guarantee the strong presence of the Action.

2.3. POTENTIAL FOR INNOVATION VERSUS RISK LEVEL

2.3.1. POTENTIAL FOR SCIENTIFIC, TECHNOLOGICAL AND/OR SOCIOECONOMIC INNOVATION BREAKTHROUGHS

The Action network comprises of many devoted, reliable participants who have access to funding to carry out the research facilitated by this Action such that any risks associated with key human resources are unlikely. The diversity of the Action's countries is both a source of risk (different cultures and systems) and a source of innovation. The Action includes at least one country where evolution is extremely controversial: risks here include that researchers and educators from this country might be prevented from contributing to or accessing the Action and its outputs. This risk, however, seems minimal at the moment and the involvement of target groups in this country would be a great source of innovation. Furthermore, the diversity of the Action is also a great source of innovation: a single country or stakeholder alone could not achieve the mandate of this Action. The Action is aimed at one of the most fundamental abilities that all members of a developed society should have: scientific literacy. This is one of the most important skills for generating an informed, knowledge-centred society. The activities of the Action will lay the groundwork for future collaborations between relevant stakeholders and facilitate the development of new research that can apply for Horizons 2020 funding such as the Scientists with and for Society call. Over the long term, the Action will likely inspire policy changes, shifts in educational practices, new ways of collaborating on scientific literacy and practices, and new approaches to education.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK PLAN

3.1.1. DESCRIPTION OF WORKING GROUPS

The groundwork for the Action is laid by Working Group (WG) 1 which, by assessing the European public's acceptance and understanding of evolution, is essential to the further workings of the Action. Each of the remaining WGs will focus on one of the four main stakeholders of the Action: (1) formal educators, (2) informal educators, (3) media and (4) scientists. The media will also act as a **lever** to reach another important stakeholder, policy makers. They will also advise on policy briefs that each group will be responsible for. Each WG will meet face-to-face twice a year and online (e.g., via Skype) on a monthly basis. Although not mandated, it will be recommended that the WGs use collaborative working tools such as Google Docs, Google Drive or the equivalent.

To ensure cooperation between the WGs and to address interrelations between their topics, cross-WG synthesis measures in the form of joint tasks and deliverables will be mandated. Each WG will allocate time for these activities and specific cross-WG exchange slots that enable all Action members to meet will be designated during plenary sessions. Links between the WGs will also be strengthened by including non-specialists from each different stakeholder group in each WG. All work and the minutes from each WG will also be made available to all Action members (e.g., via the website) and on the chosen

collaborative working platform. The meetings and STSMs will also provide an opportunity for cross-pollination of ideas by having each WG present their current results. To facilitate these interactions, maintain interest and promote collaboration, internal communication channels (e.g. newsletters and social media) between different WGs about their activities, challenges and achievements will be set up.

WG1 Assessment will focus on designing and benchmarking effective methods of gauging the understanding and acceptance of evolution and their relationship, especially in the context of overall scientific literacy. This objective will involve both the conceptual development of survey and statistical tools, and the proper processing of the resulting data (its transformation, visualization and dissemination).

Task 1: Performing a systematic review of existing methods and survey results directly related to the topic of evolution acceptance and understanding.

Task 2: Developing and translating a set of standardized tools aimed at measuring the acceptance and understanding of evolution as well as related factors across different levels of education.

Task 3: Pilot study of the standardized tools on a small scale in different European countries.

Task 4: Disseminating existing and future data in the most compelling and publicly accessible way (including popular science outputs and papers in targeted scientific journals).

Deliverable 1: Report and academic paper on existing methods and results (Task 1).

Deliverable 2: Standardized and ready-to-use protocols (e.g., survey design, questionnaire(s), procedures, data preparation and statistics) in Action Members' European languages (Tasks 2).

Deliverable 3: Academic paper on pilot results of standardized tool (Task 3).

Deliverable 4: Visual summary & press release of assessment results for media and policy makers (Task 4).

WG2 Formal Education Researchers will assess how important evolution teaching is in school curricula across Europe and identify common misconceptions held by teachers and students that could undermine evolution teaching and acceptance.

Task 1: A WG meeting dedicated to examining the schools' curricula from the participating countries and focusing on a) the ages at which evolution is taught, b) the allocated time for evolution teaching, c) the content and accuracy of the evolutionary concepts and d) potential contexts to learn about evolution using existing curricula and links to daily life/societal issues.

Task 2: Construct a questionnaire to gather data regarding teachers' CK and PCK to teach about evolution and their attitudes and self-efficacy beliefs to teach this subject.

Task 3: Fostering cooperation among educators and researchers from the participating countries to collect and analyse data regarding the way that evolution is presented in school textbooks.

Task 4: Establishing STSMs that will identify and evaluate methodologies, strategies, events and formal and non-formal contexts used to empower teachers of different grades to teach about evolution. Best practices will be identified and disseminated.

Deliverable 1: Academic paper and report on the comparative results of the analysis of the schools' curricula with suggestions to explore evolution from elementary school. Results will also be presented in the media in each country's language (Task 1).

Deliverable 2: Academic paper on the comparative results of teachers' and students' misconceptions about evolution and the socio-cultural factors that might have influenced them as well as of the analysis of the students' understanding about evolution across different developmental stages to inform curriculum design (Tasks 2).

Deliverable 3: Academic paper on the manner in which school textbooks present evolution together with proposals increasing its efficacy (Task 3).

Deliverable 4: Academic paper that evaluates the strategies used in initial teacher training and professional development actions on science and evolution education together with reports containing recommendations to enhance science and evolution teaching skills in different countries (Task 4).

WG3 Informal Educators will focus on identifying and examining the best practices in science exhibits on evolution as well as effective messages increasing the understanding of evolution and scientific literacy in general across Europe.

Task 1: Organizing a WG meeting to identify science exhibitions, exhibits and activities that present evolution-related topics and retrieve any available assessment data on their impact.

Task 2: Organizing a workshop that will establish a set of best practices/guidelines for creating/restructuring museum exhibitions, exhibits and educational programs on evolution.

Task 3: Organizing a workshop that will explore assessment strategies to evaluate evolution exhibits (in collaboration with WG1).

Task 4: Establishing STSMs that will focus on effective links and activities that could reinforce learning both in- and outside of the classroom.

Deliverable 1: Academic papers on the assessment of informal learning environments in evolution education (Task 1).

Deliverable 2: Publication and dissemination of a set of best practices for creating/revising museum exhibitions, exhibits and educational programs (Task 2).

Deliverable 3: Report of pilot study of assessment of evolution exhibits (Task 3).

Deliverable 4: Dissemination of a selection of evolution-based activities that can be used both in- and outside of the classroom for teachers and the informal education community (Task 4).

WG4 Media will focus on finding the best practices to link the scientific and educational communities with journalists, publishers and the media in general to produce powerful, compelling and effective messages that increase the understanding of evolution and of scientific literacy in general.

Task 1: Organizing an initial STSM that will collect data on the current state of science-journalism and science-media relationships in different countries and search for existing initiatives in this area.

Task 2: Promoting links between scientists and journalists/publishers in communicating evolutionary biology by means of a workshop for both groups that will examine themes including how to find potential matches between scientists and journalists or whether to credit scientists as co-authors or external experts.

Task 3: Organizing a workshop that will design a set of best practices for public media and publishers to demystify evolutionary biology and to present it as a modern, valuable and contributory field.

Task 4: Collation of best practices for science-media relationships.

Deliverable 1: A guide/compendium of effective and successful strategies linking scientists and journalists in various countries (Task 1).

Deliverable 2: An online list of projects that would benefit from a close science-media relationship (Task 2).

Deliverable 3: Reproducible ready to replicate Science-Media Training School (Task 3).

Deliverable 4: A code of good practices in science journalism (Task 4).

WG5 Scientists will focus on ensuring researchers' engagement in outreach and in evolution in particular. The WG aims to provide a sound understanding of current practices involving researchers' engagement in scientific outreach, to increase awareness about the benefits for both researchers and the general public from their interactions and to promote efficient interactions.

Task 1: Undertaking a systematic review of the ways in which researchers can be involved in outreach and develop a set of good practices that improve science and evolution literacy.

Task 2: Development of standardized tools to enhance researcher engagement in outreach.

Task 3: Develop material to enhance researcher engagement in outreach.

Task 4: Organize a joint meeting with existing COST Action on citizen science to explore citizen-science projects with an evolutionary focus.

Deliverable 1: Report and paper reviewing researcher outreach engagement and containing key recommendations on how to encourage researchers' outreach engagement (Task 1).

Deliverable 2: Ready to apply assessment toolkit for science outreach events (Task 2).

Deliverable 3: Best practice guide and recommendations for scientists' engagement (Task 3).

Deliverable 4: A compendium/ best-practices guide to citizen-science projects in evolution (Task 4).

3.1.2 GANTT CHART

Fig. 2. GANTT chart. The attainment of key milestones is marked by an "x" on the GANTT chart

Fig. 2. GANTT chart cont.

Overarching per Quarter (Q)	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Q13	Q14	Q15	Q16
TO.1 Cross-WG Synthesis																
DO1.1 Policy briefs regarding each stakeholders and the public							x			x						x
DO1.2 Open access edited book on public science literacy																x
TO.2 Capacity Building																
AO2.1 Short-Term Scientific Missions (STSMs)			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
AO2.2 Training School (1 TS per WG except Medias)						x	x	x		x	x		x	x		
AO2.3 Meetings WGs (1 meeting per WG per year, sometimes combined)				x	x	x	x	x		x	x		x	x		
TO.3 Dissemination and Outreach																
AO3.1 Webpage-launch + major updates			x	x				x				x				x
AO3.2 Newsletter		x	x		x		x		x		x		x		x	
AO3.3 Events at related conferences (workshops, symposia)				x			x				x				x	
AO3.4 Social media animation		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
AO3.5 Online interactive seminars (each time 1 for each WG)		x	x		x		x		x		x		x		x	
TO.4 Management																
AO4.1 Kick-off meeting		x														
AO4.2 Meetings MC		x		x		x		x		x		x		x		x
AO4.3 Meetings WGs				x	x	x	x	x		x		x		x		
AO4.4 Meetings SC (online + face to face)			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
DO4.1 Management plan + updates				x			x			x				x		
DO4.2 Dissemination plan + updates				x			x			x				x		
DO4.3 Stakeholders engagement strategy + updates				x			x			x				x		
DO4.4 Risk and contingency plan + updtaes				x			x			x				x		
DO4.5 Annual reports				x				x				x				x

3.1.4 RISK AND CONTINGENCY PLANS

Complex endeavours such as this one always involve some element of risk. Importantly, the Action’s team is ready to tackle potential problems. For example:

Risk 1: Members of different backgrounds do not cooperate. The Management Committee (MC) will mandate that each WG includes members of different backgrounds and promote a culture of mutual respect at meetings to facilitate cooperation. Importantly, the core group also includes representatives from all different stakeholder groups, which ensures a minimal of degree of cooperation.

Risk 2: The diversity of education systems, cultures and experiences in the different countries impedes communication and/or comparability. Although diversity lies at the heart of the Action as a potential source of innovation, it has some associated risk. After the 1st year, if the Action MC considers this to be a true risk, the Action will assess a reduced number of states along the gradient of the acceptance of evolution.

Risk 3: A member leaves the Action. Depending on the position of the member within the Action, WG coordinators and/or the MC will ensure a replacement by an equivalent stakeholder.

Risk 4: Schedule and cost limitations The MC will monitor delays and costs by planning the Action’s activities carefully.

3.2. MANAGEMENT STRUCTURES AND PROCEDURES

The COST Action will be managed in accordance with the “Rules for participation in and implementation of the COST activities”. The MC will supervise and coordinate the advancement of the action, ensure the production of annual reports, supervise the budget allocation and assess potential new members. The composition of the MC cannot be anticipated in advance, but key principles will guide its formation to ensure its representation and balance. It is thus expected that the MC will include:

- Up to two representatives from each of the participating countries;
- An equal-opportunity officer to promote gender balance and the integration of ECIs and ITCs both within the Action as well as in key leading positions (including Chair or co-Chair if mentorship is needed). This officer will also be responsible for encouraging family-friendly policies for all activities within the scope of the Action (e.g. meetings);
- A dissemination and outreach coordinator;

- A STMS and TS coordinator.

Following standard COST procedures, the MC will be elected at the onset of the Action. It will meet twice a year to assess and coordinate the progress of the Action and will require reports from all WGs every three months.

At the inaugural meeting, the MC will set up a Steering Committee (SC) that will be responsible for the operational and day-to-day management of the Action. The SC will include the Chair and Vice-Chairs, who will be elected at the first MC meeting; the ECI representative; the equal-opportunity officer, the dissemination and outreach, STMS and TS coordinators; and the WG Leaders. The SC will meet every quarter, preferentially through online meetings given the probable geographic distribution of its membership. The SC will monitor and ensure the progress of the Action according to the established timeframe. The SC will also ensure an effective coordination and flow of information between the WGs.

The WGs will be organized during the inaugural meeting. Each WG will elect a Leader and a Vice-Leader to coordinate the work within the WG as well as with the other WGs, notably by reporting to the SC meetings. WGs will physically meet at least once a year and will otherwise use electronic communication to coordinate and work. Meetings within the Action will be scheduled in connection with other, relevant international meetings whenever possible to facilitate face-to-face interaction. Two specifically dedicated meetings are planned for all active members.

A Dissemination Board managed by the dissemination and outreach coordinator will be responsible for the coordination of dissemination and outreach activities. An Action website will be part of this effort as well as activities on social media.

3.3. NETWORK AS A WHOLE

The professional experience and geographical diversity of the Action's members is crucial to its success as well as a great strength for fulfilling the main aim of the Challenge.

This Action is highly inter-sectoral, with members representing all the key stakeholders involved in developing scientific literacy:

- Scientists in both the biological sciences and science education funded at both national and European levels;
- Educators, from both formal education and informal education and science communicators.
- Media representatives;
- Policy makers experienced in public engagement and policy decisions.

23 countries have either participated in the preparation of the Action or indicated their willingness to be part of it, which shows the pan-European relevance of the Action. The inclusiveness ratio is 56.5%. The proper coordination and collaboration of the different stakeholders will be achieved by a variety of means, using the experience of members with a solid and established record in other COST Actions or community management. Specifically, the following practical actions will be taken:

- Each WG will include representatives of each stakeholder group;
- The community of participants will be actively integrated, notably by using social media and a collaborative platform (e.g., Ryver or Slack).

After the start of the Action, additional contributors will still be welcomed, both to increase the scope of the network, but also because of their ability to provide new input. They will be constructively integrated to fulfil the main aim of the Action.